

Vibrational-disruption of the feeding behavior of a plant pathogen vector

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Within *Auchenorrhyncha*, vibrational signals underlie interactions with conspecific and environment, and can be used to disrupt relevant behaviors. Vibrational interference with vector behaviors associated to host plant recognition and feeding could enable development of innovative management strategies. The main European vector of the fastidious bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* is *Philaenus spumarius*, which uses vibrations to communicate. In our work, a vibrational stimulus was designed based on a *P. spumarius* signal and was transmitted over a suitable host plant (sunflower). The signal significantly reduced the probing and feeding behavior of the insect vector, which is a xylem-feeder. Specifically, ca. 30% of the treated individuals did not attempt probing, while the feeding activity of probing insects was affected by the vibrational signal. Accordingly, a sex-independent reduction in ingestion of the xylem sap of ca. 67% compared to the control was recorded. The possible implications of vibrational vector behavior interferences on the epidemiology of *X. fastidiosa* and future research needs are discussed, including the possibility of applying this technique to olive plants.

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